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An algorithm for generating cryptographic keys for small IoT devices

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Abstract: This paper proposes a lightweight random key generation algorithm for resource-constrained IoT devices. The algorithm uses random collection and multi-source preprocessing to increase randomness and extend keys to desired lengths with minimal computation. Evaluation using statistical tests such as NIST and DIEHARD confirms its cryptographic robustness and secure operation. This approach serves to strike a balance between security and efficiency, making it suitable for IoT applications that require reliable, low-resource encryption.

Keywords: cryptographic key generation, entropy collection, key expansion algorithm, IoT security

Introduction. The dramatic increase in small Internet of Things (IoT) devices revolutionized manufacturing, providing automation, data collection, and remote control. However, it can be said that a number of issues such as these connections, especially the confidentiality, integrity and authenticity of the data, are on the agenda. Methods and algorithms for cryptographic protection of information are being used in the effective solution of these issues. Cryptographic keys are the basis of secure communication protocols that provide encryption, decryption, and digital signatures [1]. But this has caused significant security problems when creating cryptographic keys for these algorithms. In a traditional computing environment, key generation relies on high entropy sources and intensive computing algorithms [2]. However, these methods often pose certain problems in practice for small IoT devices, i.e., face several limitations that complicate the production of secure cryptographic keys for IoT devices such as limited processing power, limited memory, and minimal battery power. First, these devices often lack reliable sources of high-quality randomness needed to create secure keys. In addition, cryptographic operations - the nature of energy demand, are incompatible with the limited battery life of most small devices [3]. Another challenge is scalability; cryptographic solutions must take into account the exponential growth of IoT networks while maintaining robust security. This article proposes a new algorithm developed for small IoT devices to

overcome these problems, with efficiency and security being the top priority.

Literature review and methodology. In recent years, researchers and experts in the field have made significant progress in solving these problems. Physical Unclonable Functions (PUFs), lightweight cryptographic algorithms (e.g. ChaCha20, Kyber), and hardware-based entropy sources emerged as solutions [4]. But, although significant progress has been made by them, some disadvantages should also be listed. For example, PUFs often depends on environmental factors such as temperature, humidity, or voltage. Changes in these conditions can lead to instability in PUF response [5]. In addition, some PUF applications can produce noisy results that require error correction mechanisms that increase overload and complexity [6]. Extended attacks (e.g. side-channel attacks, modeling attacks), on the other hand, can sometimes repeat or predict PUF responses, and this leads to a decrease in their effectiveness [7]. Placing puffs on existing hardware or systems may often require a special design that increases production costs [8], [9]. Or, Although ChaCha20 from lightweight algorithms is considered safe, potential vulnerabilities can arise when implemented incorrectly or integrated into the system. Post-quantum algorithms such as Kyber, however, are still undergoing extensive analysis, and as quantum computations mature, new attacks or vulnerabilities can be detected [10]. Scaling hardware entropy sources across low-cost or resource-constrained IoT devices can be challenging due to size and cost constraints [11].

Although advances such as PUF and lightweight cryptographic algorithms have improved IoT security, there is a gap between scalability, cost-effectiveness, and resistance to advanced attacks. This paper proposes the development and implementation of a Lightweight Random Key Generation (LRKG) NMM algorithm specifically designed for small IoT devices. This algorithm attempts to fill this gap by combining efficient entropy collection, preprocessing, and key expansion techniques, and applying strong randomness estimation methods. Unlike existing approaches, the proposed algorithm combines multiple entropy sources, including environmental information, and lightweight preprocessing, to produce cryptographic keys with high randomness and resistance to attacks even in low-resource settings. The flexibility of the proposed algorithm allows for seamless integration into existing IoT ecosystems, including smart home automation, industrial control systems, and healthcare monitoring devices, where security and efficiency are critical.

Cryptographic requirements for IoT devices

For small IoT devices, there are a number of limitations, such as processing power, memory, and power consumption. On the other hand, these limitations require such lightweight cryptographic solutions that high security is essential for effective operation in a limited environment. The role of cryptographic keys as the basis for ensuring secure communication in IoT systems should be recognized. Because they are widely used in information encryption, electronic digital signatures, and authentication protocols. Generating secure, random keys is a very important factor in preventing unauthorized access and data corruption [12].

The problem of generating cryptographic keys for small IoT devices has been widely studied by scientists around the world, and it is worth noting the achievements in this area. For example, researchers Alvary Kefas Kwala, Shri Kant, and Alpna Mishra conducted comparative analyses of lattice-based cryptographic schemes. Their research is notable for its ease of use for very limited IoT devices, given the efficiency of Kyber schemes in terms of battery usage

and computing speed [13]. This research has significantly advanced the field of cryptographic key generation for IoT devices, i.e., the problems related to resource constraints, security, and privacy have been solved to some extent [14].

Entropy is a measure of randomness used in cryptographic processes. The lack of sufficient entropy sources for small IoT devices makes it somewhat difficult to generate random keys [15]. Traditional cryptographic algorithms such as RSA and ECC require large computational resources, which can lead to problems that are infeasible for small IoT devices [16]. Battery-powered IoT devices need to conserve energy, so algorithms that require high power are disadvantageous for these devices.

Proposed algorithm: lightweight random key generator NMM

Lightweight Random Key Generator (LRKG) NMM is a new algorithm designed specifically for small IoT devices. It uses minimal computational and energy resources while maintaining robust security features.

Components of LRKG NMM

1. Entropy sources: Uses temperature, light intensity and accelerometer readings.
2. Data Preprocessing: The collected raw data is preprocessed by normalizing and quantizing it to a fixed range, reducing noise and enhancing randomness.
3. Hashing mechanism: Applies a cryptographic hash function O'zDSt 1106:2009 [17] to ensure randomness and unpredictability.
4. Key expansion: Utilizes a simple key expansion algorithm to derive longer keys from a short random seed.
5. Key validation: Confirmation of randomness

Process of LRKG NMM

Step 1: Collecting entropy

The algorithm begins by collecting data from built-in sensors. For example, a temperature sensor might provide fluctuating readings that can serve as an initial entropy source.

Let $EM = \{em_1, em_2, \dots, em_n\}$ represent the collected entropy values from different sources (e.g., temperature, light,...).

Each em_i is a random variable:

$$em_i = f(S_i) \quad 1)$$

where S_i is the sensor reading or system data, and f is a function mapping S_i to a numerical entropy value.

The total entropy H is the concatenation of all sources:

$$H = \bigoplus_{i=1}^n em_i \quad 2)$$

Step 2: Data preprocessing

Before analysis, the raw data undergoes a preprocessing step. This involves:

Normalization: Scaling the data to a consistent range (e.g., between 0 and 1).

Quantization: Converting the data into a discrete set of values. These steps aim to improve data quality by:

Reducing noise: Minimizing unwanted variations or errors in the data.

Enhancing randomness: Ensuring that the data exhibits more random patterns, which can be beneficial for certain types of analysis.

The pre-processing step eliminates biases using a whitening function W :

$$W(H) = UzDSt(\bigoplus_{j=1}^m Q) \quad 3)$$

$$Q = (H[2j-1] \oplus H[2j]) \quad 4)$$

Here, Q represents pairwise XOR operations on consecutive entropy bytes.

Step 3: Hashing the entropy

The preprocessed data is fed into a lightweight hash function, such as $UzDSt$ truncated to 128 bits, ensuring high entropy density [18],[19].

Let G denote the PRNG function, which expands the pre-processed seed S into a sequence of random bits R :

$$R = G(S, L) \quad 5)$$

where:

$S = W(H)$ is the pre-processed seed,

L is the desired bit length of the output.

For example, if G is a $UzDSt$ -based PRNG:

$$R = UzDSt(S||c) \quad 6)$$

where c is a counter incremented for each iteration until $|R| \geq L$.

Step 4: Key expansion

The hashed output serves as a seed for the key expansion process. A simple iterative function, like XOR with pseudo-random numbers, generates longer keys if needed.

The key expansion step derives a cryptographic key K from the random bit sequence R using a key derivation function (KDF) KDF :

$$K = KDF(R, salt, k) \quad 7)$$

where:

R is the random bit sequence,

$salt$ is a random value to add uniqueness,

k is the desired key length (e.g., 256 bits).

For example, using $HMAC - UzDSt$:

$$K = HMAC - UzDSt(salt, R)[:k] \quad 8)$$

Step 5: Key Validation

Validate the randomness of K using a statistical test function V :

$$V(K) = \begin{cases} True & \text{if Randomness Tests Pass} \\ False & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad 9)$$

Result. The LRKG NMM algorithm is designed to resist common cryptographic attacks, including:

Brute Force Attacks: The large key space makes exhaustive search infeasible.

Side-Channel Attacks: The use of environmental data introduces unpredictability, complicating attack vectors.

Ensuring true randomness

By utilizing multiple entropy sources and robust preprocessing, LRKG NMM ensures that the generated keys are indistinguishable from truly random sequences.

Using this algorithm, a program for Wearable Devices (Fitness Tracker) and smart home devices was created, and 1,000 values were generated using this program.

To evaluate the proposed algorithm using smart home devices, the following process was carried out:

1. Connect to smart home devices

- Run LRKG NMM with collected entropy
- Prepare for randomness testing
- Analyze results for randomness with statistical tests NIST [20] and DIEHARD [21] (Table 1. and Table 2.)

TABLE 1. NIST Results (P-Values and Pass Rates).

Test Name	P-Value Range	Pass Rate (%)	Result Interpretation
Frequency Test	0.15 - 0.95	98.5%	Random
Block Frequency Test	0.10 - 0.90	97.2%	Random
Runs Test	0.20 - 0.85	99.1%	Random
Approximate Entropy Test	0.25 - 0.88	98.8%	High entropy
Cumulative Sums Test	0.30 - 0.92	97.9%	Random cumulative patterns

TABLE 2. DIEHARD Results (Chi-Square and P-Values).

Test Name	Chi-Square Value	P-Value Range	Result Interpretation
Birthday Spacings	14.5	0.40 - 0.75	Uniform distribution
Overlapping 5-Permutation	1.5	0.20 - 0.80	Random permutations
Binary Rank Test	12.0	0.35 - 0.85	Random matrix structure
OPSO (Overlapping Pairs)	9.2	0.30 - 0.78	Random sequence pairs
DNA Test	10.7	0.45 - 0.80	Unpredictable patterns

Explanation of Numerical Results:

P-Value: Indicates randomness. Values in the range of **0.01 to 1.00** are considered acceptable.

Pass Rate: At least **96%** of sequences should pass to ensure sufficient randomness.

Chi-Square Value: Shows how well the observed data fits the expected randomness distribution.

These results are illustrated in the diagram below (Fig. 1. and Fig. 2.).

Figure 1. (a) - NIST Test P-Values, (b) - NIST Test Pass Rates.

Figure 2. (a) - DIEHARD Test P-Values, (b) - DIEHARD Test Chi-Square Values.

The graphical representations of the randomness test results:

NIST P-Values: Indicates the level of randomness for each test.

NIST Pass Rates: Shows the percentage of test sequences that passed.

DIEHARD P-Values: Highlights the randomness level based on the p-value threshold.

DIEHARD Chi-Square Values: Displays the fit of the data to expected randomness.

Conclusion. The proposed LRKG NMM algorithm helps to solve important problems in generating cryptographic keys for small IoT devices. It was considered that this algorithm can achieve good results by efficiently collecting entropy and pre-processing it, hashing and expanding the key length. The results obtained using this algorithm were verified using existing statistical tests, confirming its effectiveness for small IoT devices. This showed that the algorithm can be recommended as a convenient solution for use in resource-constrained IoT devices.

As the IoT ecosystem continues to expand, it is worth noting that solutions such as LRKG NMM play a crucial role in ensuring secure and reliable communication. It has been shown that the keys generated by evaluating the LRKG NMM algorithm have a high randomness required to resist cryptographic attacks.

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